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D6.6 Data Steward Instructor Training

Work Package	WP6
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Disclaimer

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

CODATA	The Committee on Data for Science and Technology
DMP(s)	Data Management Plan(s)
ECR	Early Career Researcher
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
HEI	Higher Education Institution
ICTP	International Centre for Theoretical Physics
MOOC	Massive Open Online Course
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDM	Research Data Management
RI	Research Institution
VLE	Virtual Learning Environment

Executive Summary

The data steward instructor training events were initially designed to complement the CODATA-RDA Schools for Research Data Science. The objective was to determine the optimal form of training for Data Stewards. They were meant to be run in parallel with the schools, giving the opportunity for Data Stewards and ECRs to work together. After an initial pilot run in partnership with the ICTP in Trieste it became clear that this approach was not viable as professional Data Stewards would not be able to commit the amount of time that ECRs are able to do in their training.

Hence there was a need to develop a more focussed and shorter delivery. Conversations with a variety of different Data Stewards (which was borne out in surveys that were done in later events) demonstrated that a) many Data Stewards have only recently started their role in their institution b) are in small teams in their institution (2-5) and are sometimes on their own.

It was clear then that these events needed to teach practical skills such as supporting the development of DMPs, pedagogy, broader issues such as responsible research and to hold on a regional basis and as a result to use them as a moment for community building within that region. This was developed in partnership with EOSC-Synergy and, to a lesser extent, EOSC Pillar. The pandemic forced a switch to online delivery that required a series of half-day meetings held over the course of a week. It also had the impact that more of these events could be run with nine online events in total being run. An additional shorter version is being piloted at the very end of the FAIRsFAIR project.

An online version for self-learning was developed on the basis of the materials developed and is being hosted on the EOSC-Synergy VLE.

In the polls described above it was also found that attendees have varying levels of confidence with respect to explaining topics being most confident about the Findability and Accessibility principles and least confident about the Interoperability and Reuse principles.

The overall recommendations are

- Developing communities of data stewards at both national and regional levels should be a priority going forward.
- A combination of formal and practical training is important. In particular introducing pedagogy is key given how much training a Data Steward must do.
- As the field of data stewardship grows it will be important to consider how best to support domain-specific data steward training and community building activities.

Table of contents

1. Introduction	6
2. Data Steward Instructor training events	6
3. Findings on attendees and their Data Stewardship roles	9
4. Outline of finalised training	15
5. Data Stewards Online course developed	17
6. Recommendations	17
7. Bibliography	18
Annex 1	19

1. Introduction

The data steward instructor training was initially designed to complement the CODATA-RDA Schools for Research Data Science giving the opportunity for Data Stewards and ECRs to work together. Started in 2016, these data science schools covered a broad and shallow curriculum to introduce early career researchers to the basic tools of data science. In addition to technical modules (such as R, data visualisation and machine learning), students received instruction in topics such as research data management, open and responsible research and reproducible authorship. These schools ran over a two week period with the students in residence.

The first iteration of the data steward instructor training ran in the second week of the data science schools. After attending the first week of data science lectures, the data steward participants received a week of intensive training in key topics relating to data stewardship. While student feedback from this pilot was positive, it was noted that professional data stewards would struggle to commit to a 2 week programme.

In response to the feedback the training was re-designed to focus solely on topics relating to data stewardship. This training was subsequently run as 3 shorter half-day sessions spread across one week. As the roll-out of the revised data stewardship training coincided with the COVID-19 pandemic, this training was conducted online using a combination of pre-recorded lessons, live Zoom sessions and homework.

The wealth of recorded material and additional teaching resources accrued through running the schools in 2020 and 2021 became a resource in its own right. In late 2021 the recordings were edited and annotated in order to facilitate the development of a MOOC. This MOOC was developed in collaboration with the EOSC Synergy project using the Moodle platform, and is hosted on the project website. This will ensure the longevity of the MOOC after the end of the FAIRsFAIR project.

2 The Data Steward Instructor Training events

FAIRsFAIR aimed to deliver a set of five train-the-trainer events for Data Stewards over the life of the project. The purpose of these workshops was to support the development of data stewardship skills among staff in HEIs and other research performing organisations. A key aim of each workshop was to empower those new to the role and to help foster a network of peers where best practices

can be exchanged and those with more experience can share their knowledge with those just getting started.

The first Data Stewardship strand was delivered in August 2019 in parallel with the CODATA-RDA Research Data Science School. This session was not planned in the description of work and was run as a pilot to help the FAIRSF AIR team assess the value of existing RDM and data stewardship training materials and to help identify where additional training materials may be needed. The session was delivered by DANS and the DCC drawing on their portfolio of previous training materials and practical exercises. The agenda for the pilot Data Stewardship training session is included as annex 1. We identified pedagogy as a gap in the portfolio of training materials available within the consortium members and sought to work collaboratively with EOSC Synergy¹ to fill this gap with the materials they were developing on this topic within their own project. We also worked with [EOSC-Pillar](#) to deliver several sessions and to share details of the training materials catalogue they developed and how it might be used to support local training activities.

FAIRSF AIR, EOSC Synergy and EOSC Pillar collaborated on delivering three national level Data Stewardship training sessions and two open sessions delivered over 2021. For the national level training sessions, FAIRSF AIR also collaborated closely with local networks to plan and deliver the sessions. The aim of the national level training sessions was primarily to introduce participants to the key concepts and drivers for Open Science, RDM and FAIR data, to consider the existing local support service they can leverage, and to identify areas where collaboration with peer institutions on support provision may be beneficial. The workshops combined a series of theoretical and practical sessions, where participants were given the opportunity to interact and get to know other colleagues in their professional network and exchange their experience in supporting researchers with RDM. Participants were also introduced to key concepts of pedagogy and were able to put these in practice with a course design and development activity.

In late 2021, two open training sessions were delivered using the standard three day format described in [section 4](#) outline of finalised training. An open call allowed anyone interested to apply for a place on one of the two courses. This ensured that a broader range of Data Stewards could be supported than was possible with the national level sessions. The first open training session was run during the morning while the second session was run later in the afternoon to accommodate participants across different time zones. Each of the two open training session cohorts was expected to be geographically diverse and, accordingly, only one applicant per institution was accepted.

In recognition that increasing capacity for Data Stewardship is a global issue, two dedicated

¹ <https://www.eosc-synergy.eu/>

sessions were run outside of Europe. The first was for the Universidad Nacional de Costa Rica and the second for the Open University of Botswana. Both of these sessions aimed to cover the standard aspects covered in the three day programme but also aimed to provide a focus on developing and implementing RDM policies.

One train-the-trainer session was run for the University of Manchester which included the standard content on RDM, FAIR and Open Data on Day one and responsible research on Day three. However, as Manchester is quite advanced Day two focused more on reviewing existing support systems, workflows and resources already in place so that discussions might explore optimisation of services to enable FAIR.

A final session will be piloted for Teesside University just before the end of the FAIRSFAR project in February 2022 to deliver a condensed version of the course materials as a two-hour, high level session for new staff.

A full list of the Data Stewardship train-the-trainer sessions and a summary of the participants for each are provided in table 1.

Table 1 - summary of training events run

Host	Date run	Attendees	Hours	Notes
CODATA-RDA Research Data Science School, ICTP, Trieste, Italy ²	August 2019	6	48	Face to face pilot event, run in parallel with ECR school.
University of Manchester, UK ³	November 2020	14	3	Initial virtual event.
Universidad Nacional de Costa Rica ³	December 2020	21	3	Virtual event with introductory material.
Open University of Botswana ³	May 2021	31	3	Virtual event with introductory material.

² <https://fairsfair.eu/events/codata-rda-summer-school-research-data-science>

³ <https://fairsfair.eu/events/training/fairsfair-codata-rda-data-steward-training-series-0>

Ghent University, Belgium ⁴	June 2021	36	9	Virtual event - covering pedagogy.
National Open Research Forum (NORF), Ireland ⁵	July 2021	38	7.5	Virtual event - converging on final curriculum.
Gdańsk University of Technology, Poland ⁶	September 2021	30	9	Virtual event - with final curriculum.
Open Data Steward Instructor Training Workshop 1 ⁷	December 2021	38	8	Virtual event - open to global audience.
Open Data Steward Instructor Training Workshops 2 ⁷	December 2021	30	8	Virtual event - open to global audience.
Teesside University, UK ⁷	February 2022	15	2	Virtual event - exploring shorter curriculum.

3 Findings on attendees and their Data Stewardship roles

We saw similar patterns among the attendees for all three of the national level training sessions we delivered with regard to their length of time in post, the size of Data Stewardship teams they are part of, and their confidence levels in relation to guiding or advising on aspects of FAIR. We outline each of these areas below with our observations.

Most participants are new to their role as a Data Steward

⁴<https://fairsfair.eu/events/training/fairsfair-eosc-pillar-eosc-synergy-and-ghent-university-instructor-training-workshop>

⁵ <https://fairsfair.eu/events/fairsfair-eosc-synergy-and-norf-data-steward-instructor-training>

⁶ <https://fairsfair.eu/events/training/fairsfair-codata-rda-data-steward-training-series>

⁷ <https://fairsfair.eu/events/training/fairsfair-eosc-synergy-data-steward-instructor-training-workshops>

As noted in table 2, the majority of participants for each of the three national level training sessions had been active in their role as a Data Steward for six months or less.

Table 2 - Responses to “How long have you been in your role as a Data Steward?”

<p>Gdansk University of Technology (Poland)</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Duration</th> <th>Number of Participants</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Less than 6 months</td> <td>13</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6 - 12 months</td> <td>4</td> </tr> <tr> <td>More than 12 months</td> <td>5</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Duration	Number of Participants	Less than 6 months	13	6 - 12 months	4	More than 12 months	5
Duration	Number of Participants								
Less than 6 months	13								
6 - 12 months	4								
More than 12 months	5								
<p>National Open Research Forum (Ireland)</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Duration</th> <th>Number of Participants</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Less than 6 months</td> <td>17</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6 - 12 months</td> <td>3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>More than 12 months</td> <td>7</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Duration	Number of Participants	Less than 6 months	17	6 - 12 months	3	More than 12 months	7
Duration	Number of Participants								
Less than 6 months	17								
6 - 12 months	3								
More than 12 months	7								

Most participants are working alone or in small teams

As noted in table 3, the majority of participants for all three national level events work as part of a small team (i.e., between 2-5 people) or work alone. For the Gdansk and Ghent training sessions, the majority of participants were part of small teams at their institutions. However, the majority of participants in the NORF event were the only Data Steward at their institution. Participants from each of the three events highlighted the value of having forums such as the Data Stewardship training sessions to connect with peers and to feel part of a broader community of practice.

Table 3: Responses to “Are you part of a Data Steward team?” (The “other” option was included if this didn’t cover the attendees work arrangements.)

Gdansk University of Technology (Poland)	<p>A bar chart with four categories on the x-axis: 'No - just me!' (blue bar, 5), 'Yes - a small team (2-5 people)' (pink bar, 14), 'Yes - a big team (more than 5 people)' (red bar, 1), and 'Other?' (yellow bar, 3). The y-axis represents the number of respondents.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Count</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>No - just me!</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Yes - a small team (2-5 people)</td> <td>14</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Yes - a big team (more than 5 people)</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Other?</td> <td>3</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Count	No - just me!	5	Yes - a small team (2-5 people)	14	Yes - a big team (more than 5 people)	1	Other?	3
Response	Count										
No - just me!	5										
Yes - a small team (2-5 people)	14										
Yes - a big team (more than 5 people)	1										
Other?	3										
National Open Research Forum (Ireland)	<p>A bar chart with four categories on the x-axis: 'No - just me!' (blue bar, 14), 'Yes - a small team (2-5 people)' (pink bar, 8), 'Yes - a big team (more than 5 people)' (red bar, 2), and 'Other?' (yellow bar, 6). The y-axis represents the number of respondents.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Count</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>No - just me!</td> <td>14</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Yes - a small team (2-5 people)</td> <td>8</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Yes - a big team (more than 5 people)</td> <td>2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Other?</td> <td>6</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Count	No - just me!	14	Yes - a small team (2-5 people)	8	Yes - a big team (more than 5 people)	2	Other?	6
Response	Count										
No - just me!	14										
Yes - a small team (2-5 people)	8										
Yes - a big team (more than 5 people)	2										
Other?	6										
University of Ghent (Belgium)	<p>A bar chart with four categories on the x-axis: 'No - just me!' (blue bar, 5), 'Yes - a small team (2-5 people)' (pink bar, 11), 'Yes - a big team (more than 5 people)' (red bar, 4), and 'Other?' (yellow bar, 0). The y-axis represents the number of respondents.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Count</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>No - just me!</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Yes - a small team (2-5 people)</td> <td>11</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Yes - a big team (more than 5 people)</td> <td>4</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Other?</td> <td>0</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Count	No - just me!	5	Yes - a small team (2-5 people)	11	Yes - a big team (more than 5 people)	4	Other?	0
Response	Count										
No - just me!	5										
Yes - a small team (2-5 people)	11										
Yes - a big team (more than 5 people)	4										
Other?	0										

Most participants feel more confident about supporting findability and accessibility of research data than reuse and interoperability.

As can be seen in table 4, a similar pattern emerges across the participants of all three national level Data Steward training sessions when it comes to confidence levels on providing training and guidance in relation to the FAIR Principles. In all three events, participants rated their confidence level highest for supporting researchers on the findability of data closely followed by accessibility of research data. Participants indicated that they felt less confident about guiding researchers on aspects of reuse and least confident about supporting or advising in relation to interoperability of research data.

Table 4: Responses to “Which aspects of FAIR are you most confident about providing training and advice on (0= not confident, 10 very confident)”

<p>Gdansk University of Technology (Poland)</p>	<p>Findable (PIDs, basic description, and machine readable metadata) 7</p> <p>Accessible (access mechanism, licenses, persistent metadata) 6.4</p> <p>Interoperable (semantic vocabularies) 4.8</p> <p>Reusable (provenance, standards, open formats, curation & preservation) 5.7</p>
<p>National Open Research Forum (Ireland)</p>	<p>Findable (PIDs, basic description, and machine readable metadata) 5.8</p> <p>Accessible (access mechanism, licenses, persistent metadata) 4.8</p> <p>Interoperable (semantic vocabularies) 3.1</p> <p>Reusable (provenance, standards, open formats, curation & preservation) 4.9</p>
<p>University of Ghent (Belgium)</p>	<p>Findable (PIDs, basic description, and machine readable metadata) 6.3</p> <p>Accessible (access mechanism, licenses, persistent metadata) 6.4</p> <p>Interoperable (semantic vocabularies) 3.7</p> <p>Reusable (provenance, standards, open formats, curation & preservation) 5.2</p>

4 Outline of finalised training

The content of the Data Stewardship Instructor training was refined throughout 2021 to focus on the most essential topics required for an understanding and delivery of Data Stewardship services in a higher education setting. As a result, the content of each event varied slightly before finally settling on the format delivered for the Open Data Steward Instructor Training Workshop run in November and December 2021.

The sessions were delivered over the course of one week as three half-days. Where possible, leaving a gap of one day between each session. This approach was taken as many in Data Stewardship roles can struggle to find suitable cover to enable them to attend full day training sessions and to allow participants time to complete any homework or course preparations within their normal working hours.

Day one introduces help to build skills for training delivery and support provision. Day two introduces the concept of responsible research and focuses on how data management planning can help lead to FAIR data production. Day three switches focus to assessing local infrastructure to support FAIR and helps participants play for improvement. The modules delivered over the three half days include:

- Overview of FAIR, RDM and Open Science and how these concepts relate to each other;
- Introduction to tools to assess awareness of the FAIR principles;
- The role of data management planning to support FAIR data production;
- Understanding Responsible and Open Research;
- Assessing and planning levels of RDM service provision institutionally;
- Pedagogy in the context of teaching the above and related topics;

A category was created within the [FAIRdata Forum](#) for each training event, which was used to provide the participants with the agenda and access to the presentations, activities and other training materials used throughout the course. The image below shows the finalised timetable and topics covered during the November open call event (29th Nov - 3rd Dec 2021).

Day 1 Monday 29th November

- 09:00-09:20 Introduction and welcome ³¹
- 09:20-10:00 Overall introduction to RDM, FAIR and Open Science ³⁰
- 10:00-10:20 What does a data steward do? ²³
- 10:20-10:30 Introduction to FAIR aware tool ²³
- 10:30-11:00 Group discussion of FAIR aware tool
- 11:00-11:30 Break
- 11:30-11:50 Introduction to pedagogy ²⁰
- 11:50-12:45 Course development activity (Learning outcomes, design) ²⁶
- 12:45-13:30 Feedback on course development activity
- 13:30-13:40 Introduction to DMP exercise and close of day one ⁴³
- Homework: Choose one of the DMPs ⁴³ to review and consider if/how it might be improved to reflect FAIR.

Day 2 Wednesday 1st December

- 09:00-09:10 Brief recap of day 1 and introduction to day 2 aims and structure
- 09:10-10:00 Understanding Responsible and Open Research: Roles for Data Stewards ¹⁷
- 10:00-10:10 Short break
- 10:10-10:15 Introduction to DMP group activity ⁴³
- 10:15-10:45 DMP group activity
- 10:45-11:00 DMP activity - Discussion & Feedback
- 11:00-11:30 Feedback from breakout teams on training session
- Homework Read through RISE guide - (section on Using capability models for self-assessment and planning) ²²

Day 3 Friday 3rd December

- 09:00-09:10 Brief recap of days 1 and 2 and introduction to day 3 aims and structure
- 09:10-09:30 Introduction of RDM service model and group discussion on challenges/issues ¹¹
- 09:30-09:35 Introduction to RISE group activity
- 09:35-10:00 Group activity based on RISE model ⁸
- 10:00-10:15 Short break
- 10:15-10:30 Feedback from group activity based on RISE model
- 10:30-10:50 Group discussion on future actions and goals
- 10:50-11:00 Summary and wrap up

Figure 1: timetable for the November Open Data Steward Instructor Training Workshop (29th November to 3rd December 2021).

Events run at a national and regional level were tailored to meet the needs of the host organisation and may have included some additional sessions not outlined in Figure 1. This included the addition of a presentation or panel session discussing FAIR and Open Science practices and policy in the national setting. Any focus on national policies and requirements was removed from the two Open Data Steward Instructor Training Workshops run in November & December 2021, due to the range of nations represented during both events.

5 Data Stewards Online course developed

During the data steward instructor training events it became clear that there was high demand for training, exceeding what could be practically delivered in the time frame of the project. For this reason, the decision was made to develop a self-directed [online course](#)⁸ to help fill this demand and provide ongoing training opportunities following the end of the project. Description of the course, structure and content has been outlined in the deliverable “D6.4 Final report on competence centre with knowledge base” (Kayumbi *et al.*, 2022).

In addition to this materials for the course are available on fairdataforum.org and have been uploaded to Zenodo under the [FAIRSFAR community](#).

6 Recommendations

The lessons learnt through the roll-out of the data steward instructor training through the FAIRSFAR project highlight current challenges for expanding data stewardship within research. In particular, the survey responses discussed above indicate that many data stewards work alone or in very small teams within their institutions. Moreover, many are new not only to their roles within the institutions. The surveys indicate that these challenges exist across Europe. Training events, together with other networking opportunities, thus serve an important role in connecting data stewards and facilitating the sharing of expertise. Developing communities of data stewards at both national and regional levels, such as setting up communities of practice, agreeing to share teaching practice, or simply setting up a forum or mailing list, should be a priority going forward.

Many individuals currently in data stewardship positions have moved laterally from research, and are new to data stewardship as a formal practice. Formal training in key topics is therefore of considerable benefit. It is important to note that training thus serves not only to upskill data stewards in key topics, but also to teach them how to teach data stewardship practice to researchers within their institutions. Including topics relating to pedagogy, teaching tools and practical exercises that can be incorporated into future teaching is thus of considerable importance.

The data steward training provided through the FAIRSFAR project was not domain specific. Not only were the events designed to appeal to a broad spectrum of data stewards, but most of the participants themselves were not working in discipline-specific roles. Nonetheless, as the field of data stewardship grows it will be important to consider how best to support domain-specific data steward training and community building activities.

⁸ <https://moodle.learn.eosc-synergy.eu/course/view.php?id=132§ion=0#tabs-tree-start>

7. Bibliography

Kayumbi, G., Newbold, E., Yates, K., Whyte, A., Molloy, L., Cepinkas, L., Walker, B., 2022, Final report on competence centre with knowledge base, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6119392>

Annex 1: FAIRsFAIR Data Stewardship Strand, CODATA-RDA School of Research Data Science, August 12-14, 2019

Instructors:

- Joy Davidson, Digital Curation Centre (DCC), University of Glasgow
- Marjan Grootveld, Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS)
- Shanmugasundaram Venkataraman (Venkat), DCC, University of Edinburgh
- Steve Diggs, Scripps Institution of Oceanography
- Daniel Bangert, University of Gottingen

Participants:

- Frans Huigen, Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS)
- Ana Slavic, Open Science WG Coordinator, Eurodoc
- Sanjin Muftic, Digital Scholarship Specialist, University of Cape Town Libraries
- Cristiana Pisoni, Repository Manager, Università Degli Studi Di Bergamo
- Sothearath Seang, Policy Officer and future Open Science Ambassador, Eurodoc

Agendas

August 12		Speaker/Facilitator
08:30-10:00	Welcome and introductions	All
09:30-10:00	Background	Joy
10:00-10:30	What does a data steward do?	Marjan
10:30-11:00	Coffee Break	
11:00-11:30	FAIR data	Marjan
11:30-13:00	Using FAIR data	Steve
13:00-14:00	Lunch Break	
14:00-15:00	FAIR assessment tools - FOSTER course and exercise	Joy
15:00-15:50	Data Management Planning	Venkat
15:50-16:00	Feedback discussion for day one	Marjan

August 13		Speaker/Facilitator
09:00-10:00	Data Management Plan Activity	All
10:00-11:00	Coffee Break and group photo	
11.00-12.00	Metadata and description activity	Joy
12.00-12.30	Licences	Marjan
12:30-13:00	Repositories	Marjan
13:00-14:00	Lunch Break	
14:00-14.45	Certification: FAIR data in Trustworthy repositories	Marjan
14:45-15:00	Repositories activity	Marjan
15:00-16:00	RDM service development and optimisation and RISE activity	Venkat
16.00-16.30	Coffee Break	
16:30-17:30	RISE activity continued and report back	Venkat
17.30-18.00	Feedback discussion for day two	Joy

August 14		Speaker/Facilitator
09:00-10:30	Developing RDM policies and activity	Joy
10.30-11.00	Coffee Break	
11.00-11.30	Promote and archive data	Marjan
11.30-12.15	Upload your data	Marjan
12.15-13.00	Exercise	Marjan
13.00-14.00	Lunch Break	
14:00-14:45	Exercise on data access	Marjan
14:45-15:15	Discussion of data access challenges	Joy, Marjan, All
15:15-15:45	Designing RDM training activity	All
15:45-16:00	Feedback discussion and wrap-up Homework: develop an action plan for return to work	All

August 15th shared session with CODATA-RDA school on Computational Infrastructures.

August 16		Speaker/Facilitator
09:00-10:00	Linked Data theory and basics	Daniel
10:00-10:30	Ontologies	Daniel
10.30-11.00	Coffee Break	
11:00-11.30	Ontologies (continued)	Daniel
11:30-12:00	Producing RDF (exercise)	Daniel
12:00-12:30	SPARQL (exercise)	Daniel
12:30-13:00	Summary and feedback discussion	Daniel, Venkat, All